

THE USE OF FALL CONE SLOPE IN ESTIMATION OF CLAY CONTENT

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ABSTRACT

The active and inactive clay content are delineated at a clay index of zero. The soil with a positive clay index is active clay, while the soil with a negative clay index is inactive clay. The soil with a positive clay index (active clay) is correlated to the liquid limit and plasticity index. In contrast, soil with a negative clay index (inactive clay) is not correlated with the liquid limit and plasticity index. This paper presents a model that predicts the clay content based on the correlation between the clay content of the soil with a positive clay index and the average fall cone slope (20/LL). The model was meticulously developed after analyzing 307 Atterberg limits and clay content test results collected from thirteen different literature. The proposed model was found to compute the clay content with an accuracy of 87% (87% of the calculated clay content results were within the statistical testing bound of $\pm 12\%$ given in AASHTO T88-10), ensuring its robustness.

INTRODUCTION

The laboratory determines the clay content following standard procedures outlined in BS 1377 or AASHTO T88-10. These methods, widely used in material testing laboratories, provide a general understanding of the clay content in a soil sample. However, despite its importance, this test is performed in a few specialized material testing laboratories and thus is not part of the on-site quality control tests. One major disadvantage of clay content determination is its inability to discern active clay from inactive clay. Therefore, both methods (BS 1377 and AASHTO T88-10) determine total clay content, including inactive non-clay mineral clay-sized particles and active clay.

The correlation between the average fall cone slope and the plasticity index is a key aspect that motivated the proposed model's development. As Maregesi (2023,2024) demonstrated, the inactive and active clay is delineated at the clay index of zero. Soil with a negative clay index contains a

substantial amount of inactive clay, which dilutes the activity of clay minerals to less than one, leading to no correlation between the liquid limit/plasticity index and clay content. Conversely, soil with a positive clay index is predominantly active clay, and the liquid limit/plasticity index is highly correlated to the clay content. This correlation, which is also reflected in the average fall cone slope, underscores the validity and reliability of the proposed model.

While the method of determining clay content poses challenges due to the inclusion of inactive and active clay, the proposed model offers a practical solution. Separating the inactive clay content from the active clay content makes it possible to mathematically model the relationship between the plasticity index and clay content. This enhances our understanding of soil mechanics and provides a useful tool for predicting the amount of clay within the soil matrix.

The slope of the fall cone curve progressively decreases as the moisture content decreases. The decrease in slope tends to quasi-stabilize at penetration values of less than 5 mm (Maregesi, 2022). It is hypothesized that for any soil, zero moisture content corresponds with zero fall cone penetration value; therefore, the average fall cone slope can be computed using coordinates (0,0) and (LL,20). This slope is invariant and measures the rate of change of soil shear strength as moisture content varies. The average fall cone slope, as defined in equation 1, is highly correlated with the plasticity index. The plasticity index varies depending on the type of clay minerals within the soil matrix. The average fall cone slope can be used to identify the type of clay minerals within the soil matrix and can also be used to estimate the amount of clay within the soil matrix (Maregesi, 2022, 2023). For instance, soil with an average fall cone slope of less than 0.16 is likely to be montmorillonite, while soil with an average fall cone slope of more than 0.56 is likely to be kaolinite. The average fall cone slope of illite, a mixture of clay minerals or a binary mixture of kaolinite and

montmorillonite, is within the range of 0.16-0.56 (Maregesi, 2023). This paper presents a model that estimates the clay content using the correlation between the average fall cone slope and clay content. A total of 307 Atterberg limits and clay content test results collected from the literature were analyzed, and 172 selected test results with positive clay index were used for developing a model. The test results used during this analysis were collected from Reddy et al. (2020) -45 test results, Cerato et al. (2006) -4 test results, Prakash et al. (2012) – 9 test results, Sridharan et al.,(2000) – 4 test results, Vincent et al. (2021) -6 test results, Otoko (2014)- 12 test results, Widjaja et al. (2020)- 21 test results, Sridharan et al. (1986)-7 test results, Spagnoli et al. (2018) – 76 test results, Afolagboye et al. (2021) – 75 test results, Karakan (2020)- 34 test results, Mishra (2012) – 13 test results, Sridharan et al. (1988) – 5 test results and Reznik (2016)- 5 test results.

$$\text{Average fall Slope} = \frac{20}{LL} \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

LL is the liquid limit.

DEVELOPMENT OF MODEL OF COMPUTING CLAY CONTENT

Casagrande cup and fall cone methods of determining the liquid limits give different liquid limit values. Thus, the computed plasticity index also differs. However, this study assumes that both methods yield the same results.

This study reveals a significant correlation between the clay index and average fall cone slope, as depicted in Figure 1. This correlation is particularly strong for soil with a positive clay index but weakens considerably for soil with a negative clay index, as evidenced in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Variation of clay index and average fall cone slope (20/LL)

Figure 2: Variation of the average fall cone slope and negative clay index

Figure 3 shows a good correlation between the positive clay index and fall one slope, supporting the earlier conclusion reached by Maregesi (2023, 2024) that the clay index of zero is the value that delineates the inactive and active clay. Therefore, considering that the average fall cone slope can be used to estimate the plasticity index (Maregesi, 2022), the average fall cone slope can be used to estimate the clay content for soil with a positive clay index because the plasticity is imparted to the soil by the presence of the active clay within the soil matrix.

Figure 4 presents a complex interplay between the average fall cone slope and the clay content for soils with both negative and positive clay index. Despite a broad trend suggesting a decrease in clay content as the average fall cone slope increases, the correlation between the two is notably weak. The scattered data poses a significant challenge, rendering the creation of a comprehensive mathematical model to represent the relationship unattainable.

Figure 5 provides further evidence to support the earlier conclusion, demonstrating the variation in average fall cone slope and clay content for soil with a negative clay index. As expected, there is no correlation between the average fall cone slope and clay content in such soil because a significant amount of the inactive clay mineral is present, which does not contribute to the soil's plasticity but is classified as clay due to its particle size being less than 0.002 mm. Importantly, it is noted that soil with an average fall cone slope of less than 0.16, classified as montmorillonite clay, has a positive clay index, reaffirming the earlier conclusion that montmorillonite is an active clay mineral and has a positive clay index.

Figure 6 shows a correlation between the average fall cone slope and clay content for soil with a positive clay index. It can be seen that the average fall cone slope is highly correlated to the clay content, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination of 0.8881 fitted using the exponential function shown in equation 2. Since the average fall cone slope is highly correlated to the clay content for soil with a positive clay index, then equation 2 can be used to compute the clay content for soils with a positive clay index. The same equation can be used to compute the equivalent active clay

content for soil with a negative clay index, which imparts plasticity to the soil. Thus, the proposed model can be used to determine the amount of active clay in the soil with a negative clay index, making it possible to discern the amount of inactive clay within the soil matrix making it possible to report both active and inactive clay content during the clay content determination.

$$clay = 101.5979e^{-3.9938(\frac{20}{LL})} \dots \dots (2)$$

Equation 2 shows that the clay content can be estimated using the liquid limit as the sole predictor of the clay content within the soil matrix.

Figure 3: Variation of average fall cone slope and positive clay index

Figure 6 shows that the amount of active clay within the soil matrix varies depending on the type of clay minerals. The clay content of the montmorillonite clay is more than 40%, while the active clay content of the kaolinite clay mineral is less than 20%. Soil with 25-40% active clay content is occupied by illite clay or a mixture of clay minerals, including the binary mixture of kaolinite and montmorillonite. Based on the zoning of clay content shown in Figure 6, it is evident that active clay content can be used to identify the type of clay minerals within the soil matrix.

Figure 4: The variation between the average fall cone slope and the clay content

Figure 6: The correlation between average fall cone slope and clay content for soil with positive clay index ($R^2=0.8881$)

Figure 5: Variation of the average fall cone slope and clay content for soil with negative clay index

COMPUTATION OF THE ACTIVE CLAY CONTENT

The clay content of the soil with a positive clay index was computed using Equation 2. Figure 7 presents the variation of the calculated clay content and the residual plot. Notably, 87% of the test results plot within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 , as specified in AASHTO T 88-10, further demonstrating the robustness of the proposed model.

Figure 8 provides a comparison between the calculated and determined clay content. The model's ability to reasonably predict the clay content is evident. Figure 9, a histogram plot, reveals that approximately 90% of the residuals are within the statistical testing bound. Notably, the residual is normally distributed, affirming that the model adheres to the principle of constant variance.

Figure 7: Residual plot showing the difference between the determined and computed clay

Figure 9: comparison between the determined and computed clay content

Figure 9: Residual histogram

CONCLUSION

The proposed mathematical model, which computes the clay content reasonably well, is developed based on the assumption that the fall cone and Casagrande cup methods yield essentially the same liquid limit and plasticity index values.

The active and inactive clay is delineated at a clay index of zero, such that the soil with clay with a positive clay index is active clay while the soil with a negative clay index is inactive clay.

The average fall cone slope strongly correlates to the clay content for soil with a positive clay index. This practical correlation allows the model proposed in this study to be a valuable tool for computing the soil matrix's clay content.

For soil with a negative clay index, the average fall cone slope may not be correlated to the clay content. However, the model proposed in this study proves its comprehensive applicability by accurately computing the equivalent active clay content, which is crucial in discerning the active and inactive clay content.

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